

Analytical and experimental investigation of a H₂O₂-HDPE hybrid autophage engine

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Abstract

This paper presents the advancement of the maturation of hybrid autophage rocket propulsion through AMBRE, the first small-scale prototype of a hybrid autophage launcher. This architecture involves the use of the launcher's fuel as a structure, removing the need for tanks and halving the rocket's dry mass. During flight, the length and the mass of the rocket continuously decrease, resulting in a single-stage-to-orbit launcher with a better overall performance and reduced cost thanks to its simpler design and logistics. Following the firing tests conducted in January 2024 by Alpha Impulsion, the integration of the autophage engine continues with several developed subsystems. Insertion of propellants is achieved thanks to an electric embedded system developed and patented by Alpha Impulsion, introducing the possibility of throttling the engine. This solution was estimated most effective for orbital flight in a previous theoretical work and a prototype was tested for integration in the autophage engine of AMBRE. The insertion system developed is, at the state of the art, the first system allowing the use of hybrid autophage technology in flight. This paper highlights the advancements made in the development of AMBRE towards its first experimental launch and the research and development roadmap ahead. The project will prove the concept of hybrid autophage propulsion, paving the way for a larger scale orbital prototype.

Keywords: Autophage Propulsion, Hybrid Rocket Engines, Solid Propellant Insertion System, Polymer Fuel

Nomenclature

Acronyms

HTPB Hydroxyl-terminated polybutadiene
O/F Oxidizer/Fuel Mass ratio
PE Polyethylene (HDPE, LDPE, UHMWPE)

Symbols

\dot{m} Mass flow rate
 \dot{r} Fuel regression rate
 D Diameter
 I_v Specific impulse per unit volume $\rho_m I_{sp}$
 L Length
 P Power
 p pressure
 r/t radius to thickness ratio of a hollow cylinder
 T Thrust
 t thickness of the fuel tube
 v_a Autophage velocity (same as insertion velocity)

Greek symbols

γ acceleration due to thrust
 ρ density

Subscripts

ch chamber
 e engine
 fu fuel
 i initial
 ins insertion
 m mean, average
 ox oxidizer
 p propellants
 u upper

1. Introduction to autophage propulsion

1.1 State of the art, objectives

Autophage propulsion, in contrast to the conventional concept of rocket staging, involves the continuous reduction of the rocket's structural mass throughout its flight. Typically, this is achieved by incorporating designs that feed the rocket's fuselage to the rocket engine. It results in a vehicle that steadily diminishes in length until nothing remains between the rocket engine and the upper part. In 1960, Z.A. Typaldos [1] patented the first single-stage autophage concept. The solid grain and metallic fuselage would be passively inserted into the chamber by the inertia of the rocket against the engine's thrust. Other untested early concepts were reviewed in a previous article [2]. Modern research efforts began in the early 2000s in Oles Honchar Dnipro National University (Ukraine) and University of Glasgow (UK), encompassing experimental investigation of an engine prototype and system analysis for trajectory and thermal aspects ([3, 4, 5, 6]). The concept uses unmixed solid propellants: an oxidant powder (like NH_4ClO_4) stored in a combustible tube (polyethylene PE or polypropylene). The rod of propellants is vaporized against a solid surface able to conduct heat from the main chamber that burns the vaporized fuel.

Research continued at University of Glasgow on a tri-propellant autophage concept with the Ouroboros 1 to 3

\vec{F} : Thrust, \vec{F}_s : Axial force of the engine pushing the structure, \vec{U}_s : insertion velocity, \vec{U}_p : fuel regression rate

Fig. 1. Annotated Schematic of an early autophagy concept from [1].

engines, using gaseous oxygen and propane for the main flame and a thin PE tube as a secondary fuel [7]. This geometry aims to produce a bi-liquid rocket engine that will also consume a thin fuselage made of hard polymers (PEEK) or composites. The liquid propellants would be stored in concentric collapsible tanks which have benefited from proof of concept and might accommodate to the continuous reduction of the vehicle's length [8]. These works have also investigated a pulsed operation of the engine as a solution to facilitate the inertial insertion anticipated by Typaldos.

In this context, Alpha Impulsion, created in Toulouse (France), patented hybrid autophagy propulsion and presented a system level performance estimation [2]. The company aims to commercialize a launch service for smallsats at a reduced cost and environmental impact, using this patent. Indeed, hybrid propellants generally offer advantages such as safety, low cost, throttleability and environmentally friendlier processes, with reasonable performance that would synergize with the low structural index of the autophagy architecture. The founding project began in 2023 and aims to demonstrate hybrid autophagy propulsion in flight with an experimental rocket named AMBRE. The propellants used are HDPE and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2 90%). A hybrid rocket engine with a combustion chamber geometrically representative of the autophagy engine was tested in the first quarter of 2024 to obtain first combustion insights [9] and was used to design AMBRE's autophagy engine. The project is still ongoing.

This article aims to trace the progress so far in the project, from the governing principles of the concept to reviewing essential subsystems developed for AMBRE. From these enabling systems, next steps to increase the maturity of this vehicle architecture will be presented.

1.2 Basic governing principles

This section assembles the general behaviors that describe a hybrid autophagy propulsion system, that we aim to demonstrate with the AMBRE project, and that drive the design of an orbital hybrid autophagy launcher.

1.2.1 Propellant mass decoupled from dry mass

Modern autophagy propulsion relies on utilizing the launcher's structure as reaction mass. The selection of the structural propellant is crucial for any autophagy architecture. For a given fairing and rocket engine, the cross section of the combustible structure is set, leaving its length as a degree of freedom. In the case of a simple cylindrical shape, the propellant mass M_p is then limited only by the maximum aspect ratio allowable. With ρ_m as the mean density of the propellant and D the main body diameter:

$$M_p = \rho_m L \frac{\pi D^2}{4} \quad (1)$$

From Tsiolkovsky's equation:

$$\Delta V = I_{sp} \ln \left(\frac{M_i}{M_e + M_u} \right) \quad (2)$$

where $M_i = M_p + M_e + M_u$ is the lift-off mass of the rocket, M_e is the mass of the engine and M_u is the remaining non-reacting mass (upper structure, leftover fuel, fairing and payload). In the case of an autophagy launcher, it appears that any value of ΔV is attainable by adjusting the mass of propellant because it is independent from the dry mass. In practice, the required thrust to weight ratio limits the maximum propellant mass for a given engine.

Considering the acceleration of the engine at lift-off $\gamma = T/M_i$, Tsiolkovsky's equation can be re-arranged to integrate the thrust limitation of the engine:

$$\frac{M_u}{M_i} = \exp \left(-\frac{\Delta V}{I_{sp}} \right) - \gamma \frac{M_e}{T} \quad (3)$$

In the case of hybrid propulsion, the full mass of solid fuel is available to shape the fuselage, giving it a large thickness in the range of 5 to 20% of the diameter. This means that softer materials like the thermoplastics usually used in hybrid propulsion for their combustion performance can be employed. The geometry compensates for their limited mechanical properties (see results on launcher stiffness [2]). The physical architecture of the rocket can be seen in Fig. 2. The range given for the thickness is explained in the following discussion on O/F .

For a given ΔV requirement, the upper mass fraction of the rocket M_u/M_i (tightly linked to the payload capacity), increases with decreasing acceleration at lift-off γ , with increasing engine thrust-to-weight ratio T/M_e and with

Fig. 2. Schematic of a hybrid autophage launcher with the lead screw insertion system.

increasing I_{sp} , which is not different from any launch vehicle.

From the variation in propellants mass, the thrust can be expressed

$$T = \dot{m}I_{sp} = I_v v_a \frac{\pi D^2}{4} \quad (4)$$

where v_a is the velocity at which propellants are fed to the chamber, or autophage velocity, and I_{sp} and I_v denote the specific impulse (in speed unit) and volumetric specific impulse of the engine. The autophage velocity can be described as the relative velocity between the rocket engine and the fuel grain. From this, controlling propellant feed rate via v_a becomes key to both maintaining nominal thrust and throttling the engine.

1.2.2 Propellant feeding power requirement

To insert propellants and achieve control over the thrust goal, the chamber pressure must be overcome by a set of forces. Several mechanisms have been proposed to achieve linear motion of the propellants into the chamber, the first of which is the inertial effect already shown in Fig. 1. This effect was studied in [10].

The power required to feed the insertion system P_{ins} is directly linked to the thrust, performance, and chamber pressure p_{ch} of the engine,

$$P_{ins} = p_{ch} v_a \frac{\pi D^2}{4} = \frac{p_{ch}}{I_v} T \quad (5)$$

For a given required thrust with a given efficiency, the inertial effect may suffice in terms of feeding power, leaving the launcher extremely simple, with a limit on chamber pressure. In practice, that limit was found very low in the case of hybrid autophage launchers at interesting scales like minilaunchers dedicated to smallsats ($10^2 - 10^3$ kg). An active mechanism must be used in addition to provide power, and to control the flow of propellant.

For the liquid part of propellants, pumps are already a mature solution, widely used in space propulsion. For the solid part, several architectures may be envisioned. From a comparison of attainable specific power, the solution of a lead-screw directly driving the combustible fuselage as its nut, powered by an electric motor and batteries (see Fig. 2) was found most effective [2] and affordable. The efforts considered in this case make this solution sufficient to provide for the whole insertion power budget, so that no pump is needed and the oxidant can be pushed towards the combustion chamber by the mere reduction of the length of the fuselage.

The electric motor drives the screw, that engages itself in the fuselage. The system also needs a free-run stop so that rotation is indeed converted to translation. In addition, a mechanical connection between the combustion chamber and the insert system is required. That connection then takes the shape of knives cutting through the fuselage in the axial direction and preventing its rotation.

1.3 Impacts of the choice of propellants

In autophage concepts, the solid propellants shall combine interesting combustion performance and sufficient mechanical properties to act as the fuselage. The first step in defining an autophage launcher is the choice of the oxidizer, the fuel, and their mixing ratio. Most solids considered are thermoplastics as they are at the center of existing literature in hybrid propulsion research and several industrial projects. Most of them also show good mechanical strength. This is a requirement that tends to disqualify HTPB and paraffin as main autophage propulsion fuels.

1.3.1 Geometrical mixture ratio

In autophage propulsion, the average O/F ratio over the flight is related to the geometry of the fuselage. Indeed, assuming constant feed rate of both propellants, the cross section of the tube and its internal cross section govern the values of both mass flow rates and total masses. Considering cylindrical shapes, the average O/F ratio must be equal to

$$O/F = \frac{M_{ox}}{M_{fu}} = \frac{\rho_{ox}}{\rho_{fu}} \frac{(r/t - 1)^2}{2r/t - 1} \quad (6)$$

When only the lead screw system is used to control the feed rates, the liquid propellant's flow rate is determined by the reduction rate of the available volume upstream of the rocket engine, where it is stored. This volume reduces with the motion of the fuselage. This pressurizes the liquid, which is thus pressure-fed into the rocket engine. The mixture ratio cannot change from the above value, which can be set to match the peak combustion velocity of the propellants. Thus, the choice of the propellants determines the thickness of the fuselage, which then must be

validated for the mechanical loads it encounters. In order to decouple propellants feed rates, one could use a pump and a controlled vapor phase in the tank part upstream of the engine.

1.3.2 Regression of the fuselage

Obtaining freedom on the total feeding rate, and thus thrust modulation, requires the solid regression rate to be known, so that the shape of the burning fuselage may be properly contained in the combustion chamber. Indeed, the value of the regression rate will balance the autophage velocity and control the shape and size of the combustion surface.

This can be demonstrated by considering the fuselage entering at a certain \vec{v}_a inside the combustion chamber. As the grain is inserted, the combustion on its internal surface causes its thickness to decrease at a general regression rate \dot{r}_f . The regression on the internal face of the fuselage and the autophage velocity combine to create a stable combustion surface, as shown on Fig. 3. The size of the conical

Fig. 3. Regression model in the hybrid autophage engine

combustion surface is important. Indeed, the design of the combustion chamber must take into account the maximum length of the regressing surface during the mission. This regression length L_f is defined as the axial distance between the start and the end of the conical grain being regressed inside the chamber. The angle of the cone links the velocities and the geometrical parameters of the cone as follows:

$$\sin \theta = \frac{\dot{r}_f}{v_a} \quad (7)$$

$$\tan \theta = \frac{t}{L_f} \quad (8)$$

Assuming the small angle approximation, the geometry of the regressing fuel is the result of the insertion velocity imposed and the ballistic response of the fuel.

$$L_f = \frac{t v_a}{\dot{r}_f} \quad (9)$$

Oversizing the combustion chamber implies additional mass, undersizing it may result in overflowing the chamber with solid fuel, potentially breaking it. The basic modeling of this design rule is one of the goals of intermediate works in the AMBRE project, reported in a previous publication [9].

In all autophage engines, the fuselage must be vaporized to be used as reaction gas in a rocket nozzle. Depending on the solution of vaporization chosen, the regression rate \dot{r}_f , defined as the speed at which a pyrolyzing surface burns away, limits the autophage velocity allowable in the engine. A high regression rate thus enables a high autophage velocity, governed by the heating of the propellant until it reaches pyrolysis temperature. The thermal conductivity, heat capacity and pyrolysis temperature of the propellant are thus values of interest. Comparison of propellants is included in the previous report made for this congress [2].

2. Technological advancement of enabling technologies

Understanding the first principles above is one of the goals of the AMBRE project. All results stemmed from the observation of these behaviors are not available yet as the project is on-going. The following discussion reports the current advancement of the project and its impact on the technology maturation program.

No flight prototype was ever tested in any implementation of the autophage propulsion. AMBRE is aiming for a fully functional demonstration of hybrid autophage propulsion. This small experimental rocket (1kN thrust using 90%HTP/HDPE) is set to fly in early 2025.

Hybrid autophage propulsion relies on three pillars: hybrid combustion applied to a sliding fuel grain, the propellants insertion system, and the mechanics of the combustible fuselage (HDPE for AMBRE). AMBRE is a first step in all three, verifying the behavior of the hybrid rocket engine at 1kN scale, testing an insertion system based on the lead-screw and pressurizing the combustion chamber fuselage up to 7bar. The plan ahead is presented in the Future Works section.

The length of the combustion surface must be known in conditions representing the flight, to design the flight combustion chamber accordingly. This led to the development of a simple hybrid rocket engine to measure the attainable regression rate and thus, predict the regression length. Additionally, the required feeding power must be correctly estimated before an autophage engine can be fired. The lead-screw insertion system is thus developed in parallel, to perform fuselage insertion tests and verify that the electric motor is powerful enough. Pressure tests to verify the proper sealing of the sliding interface

between the fuselage and the engine were performed as well.

From these efforts, which are finished for the most part at the date of this article, the autophage engine can be assembled and ground tested before the flight-ready rocket is assembled. The future works section below will discuss the expected outcomes of these activities. Here are discussed the results of the activities on the subsystems.

2.1 Design process of AMBRE

The general sizing of AMBRE was limited by the funds available to a newly founded start-up. Yet, the design starting point was identified with technical requirements. Attainable efficiencies in the lead-screw system gave the required ratio between the electric motor driving the insertion system and the useful insertion power $p_{ch} \cdot A_{ch} \cdot v_a$. As the motor is a critical and heavy component, an objective was set to maximize its specific power in order to give as much freedom on the chamber pressure as possible. On the other hand, the rocket should be held by hands to keep operations simple, limiting the size. A motor with the best mass performance on the market in the required power range was thus chosen. As it is responsible for delivering power to the feeding system – a most critical function – the design of the rocket started from this power budget and the geometrical dimensions of this motor.

With functional demonstration as a goal and no performance requirement, high test H₂O₂ was chosen as an oxidizer because it is liquid at room temperature and can start the engine without requiring an igniter, which spares the design of that subsystem. Polyethylene was chosen as an inexpensive solution to produce grains and a well known solid fuel. From existing verifications of Marxman's law for this couple, the regression rate could be estimated.

With v_a set by the required mass flow rate to achieve the 1kN thrust of the engine, and the grain thickness set by the optimal O/F ratio (see Eq.(6)), the regression length is then set by the mean regression rate in the chamber (see Eq.(9)). The poor regression properties of the chosen couple at low oxidizer flux meant that the combustion chamber would be long, leading to an impossible mass budget at lift-off. Thus, a swirling injector in the range of $SN_g = 5$ was designed and fire-tested [9], which improved the mass to an acceptable value.

After this classic HRE test campaign, discussed in the following section, the upper part of the rocket was designed. Most of subsystems here are not specific to autophage propulsion and commonly used, like a recovery system, telemetry, and the overall control system.

Fig. 4. AMBRE model including the genuine flight combustion chamber and the combustible fuselage in orange

2.2 Preliminary firing tests

The firing test campaign of a conventional HRE using 90%HTP-HDPE was studied to validate components before the autophage engine configuration [9]. Several components were present in their final version, and one goal of the campaign was to verify their behavior and ensure predictability when testing the autophage mode in the near future. These components are the catalytic bed and swirling injector, the chamber wall and thermal protection, and the nozzle. Figure 5 shows the set up of the experiments carried out. The aim was also to predict the length of the grain during firing in autophage mode and report observations that influence the development and operation of the autophage engine.

The experimental regression rate showed a classical G_{ox} dependency, with the Marxman coefficient coherently computed with two different reduction methods. The ig-

Fig. 5. Test bench and instrumentation

ignition time exhibited a dependence on oxidizer mass flux, confirming previous outcomes in literature. Additionally, a dependence on the swirl number and impingement intensity was also suggested. A model to compute the transient of the regression length has been used as a reference to estimate the design of the combustion chamber of the autophage engine.

The code reproduces the dynamic process of the fuel grain entering the combustion chamber, in which it faces a regression field : the equilibrium state is not representative of the dynamic evolution of the burning grain and the variable volume it takes inside the combustion chamber. Instead of the spatial-time averaged \dot{r}_f , the local regression rate $\dot{r}_{f,x}$ was exploited to take into account the variation along the axial distance from the injector.

The initial shape of the fuel influenced the time required to get to the equilibrium condition. However, the estimation of the ignition time turned out to be the key parameter for the autophage configuration to properly design the combustion chamber length and to achieve the desired O/F and thrust. The ignition delay of the fuel lets the grain be fed to the combustion chamber without regressing, therefore changing the shape of the combustion surface at ignition. The time dependent code shows that tests showing 5 s or 10 s of ignition time would lead to re-

spectively 6% or 20% of regression length difference during the transient compared to its equilibrium state. Therefore, knowing the regression rate to size the combustion chamber length is not sufficient. There is the risk that during the transient before getting to the equilibrium shape, the grain could reach the end of the combustion chamber and cause overloading of the insertion system, or alternatively, that the engine fails providing the expected thrust at lift off due to smaller burning surface (in this case leaving part of the chamber exposed to the flame hot gas too).

Thanks to this analysis, the autophage engine configuration can be designed and tested in the next phase of the AMBRE project. Oversizing the combustion chamber's thermal protection thickness would mitigate the risk of a short ignition time, while pessimistic estimation of the ignition time (same order of the supposed combustion time) would provide enough safe margin of combustion chamber length. The autophage test campaign will be useful to assess thrust level at liftoff as well as understand the needs of an igniter for flight.

2.3 Insertion system tests

An insertion test campaign is part of the roadmap to validate the rocket for flight. The autophage firing test campaign, unlike the previous HRE tests, will require the embedded insertion of the propellants. Therefore, the main objective of the insertion campaign is to achieve propellant feeding into the combustion chamber while staying under the power budget given by the electric motor. The insertion system has the role to feed both propellants to the combustion chamber. As the expected pressure drop in the injector is now verified thanks to the HRE firing test results, this power budget is known.

One of the main design choices to be made is the screw-nut interface (see Fig.2). One design, facilitating watertightness at the expense of performance, was initially preferred. Indeed, H2O2 is stored directly on top of the screw, and the combustion chamber is pressure-fed from that region, making proper sealing important. The screw transmits a torque to the fuselage, which in turn transmits the torque to the part of the motor-screw assembly serving as stator. This is one of the roles of the knives traversing the fuselage. From this architecture (best explained in Fig.2), a set of resisting efforts must be characterized to ensure that the power budget is satisfied. Not considering the efforts related to fluid insertion and the useful pressurization effort, these losses include surface separation of the polymer by the knives, friction, and efforts specific to the screw design.

In the design phase, surface separation efforts were estimated with theory found in the literature [11]. Due to the high normal efforts encountered, friction was high, so the screw was coated with PTFE to reduce the friction co-

efficient to 0.1. These efforts still account for a significant fraction of the torque budget in AMBRE.

Part of these efforts can be experimentally retrieved by measuring the torque or electrical current of the motor while inserting a grain at atmospheric pressure without inserting the fluid propellant. This is a goal of the insertion campaign. A grain was engaged in the system, with a method to gradually increase the required effort to operate the assembly with the motor. The method or geometry of the real grain used for this cannot be shared.

This series of tests ultimately led to the rejection of the first design of the screw. It was then decided to re-design the screw, which should completely eliminate the previous difficulty. These new tests are scheduled for imminent completion. The insertion system was validated from the point of view of electronics and software. Once tested, the second design will validate TRL3 on the hybrid autophage engine, verifying that the insertion of a solid fuel in a combustion chamber is possible.

The insertion system is situated in close proximity to the combustion chamber, particularly the knives, which initially caused concerns regarding thermal aspects. However, the maximum temperature reached at the upper part of the engine due to the recirculating hot gas has been evaluated during the HRE test campaign [9], thereby driving the selection of their material and validating the knives' design.

2.4 Dynamic sealing of the engine

Prior to the execution of wet insertion tests, autophage tests and the launch of AMBRE, it is essential to ascertain the rocket's capability to withstand internal pressure forces and ensure watertightness. Tank pressure tests and combustion chamber pressure tests were planned. The fairing interface is utilized to close the upper part of the grain, while the bottom is secured by the internal dynamic seal between the insertion system and the tank. The pressurization of the tank confirmed that there were no leaks and demonstrated that it was able to sustain nominal and off-nominal pressure. For its test, the chamber is anchored to the tank via the designed interface. This allows the assessment of the dynamic sealing between the combustion chamber and the atmosphere, which closes the gap between the fuel grain and the chamber wall, while the bottom part of the chamber is closed by a metallic flange (nozzle sealing was verified in the HRE firing test campaign). Water is then inserted via the oxidizer feeding line of the insertion system and pressure is built up. The combustion chamber test has not yet been conducted due to difficulties inserting the screw into the grain.

3. Future works within AMBRE

Inserting propellants into a pressurized combustion chamber with an embedded system is still challenging, but the operational difficulties are being removed from the design. The new screw-nut interface design is also more compliant with future projects, including cryogenic projects, where fewer screw designs would be viable. New insertion tests will enable the execution of a cold flow test and combustion chamber pressure tests. These tests will be conducted in-house, and will validate experimentally the last of the critical function of AMBRE, namely propellant insertion, and validate TRL3.

Fig. 6. Autophage engine test bench (to be tested)

Subsequently, the autophage tests will be carried out to observe the performance of the engine. These tests will verify the engine's thrust level as well as the sealing of the chamber under firing conditions. The sizing of the flight thermal protection will be validated, and the throttleability and re-ignition transients will be observed, for their effect on the geometry of the regressing fuselage. Given the different nature of this kind of test, the autophage firing campaign will be conducted at an external facility before the end of the year (Q4 2024). This will allow verification of the predicted regression length with the fully integrated and embedded autophage engine, validating TRL4.

AMBRE is scheduled for launch in early 2025, subject

to the completion of all remaining preliminary test campaigns. During this flight, the contribution of inertial insertion may be measured, though it is expected to account only for a few percents of the total insertion effort.

4. Conclusion

The founding principles of autophage propulsion and its implementation with hybrid propulsion were reviewed. Thermoplastics may theoretically stand both the requirements of high combustion energy and high mechanical strength to produce a viable launcher with no inert structure, burning its fuselage and showing an outstanding structural index. This encouraging result needs to be verified and the AMBRE project is a first step, proposing an experimental rocket. As a milestone of this project, the HRE firing test campaign using 90% HTP-HDPE validated the behavior of the combustion chamber for the autophage engine. The regression rate shows a typical G_{ox} dependency described by a Marxman law. The upper interface of the engine could be thermally monitored to verify a reasonable heat transfer from the chamber and design the knives of the insertion system accordingly. A variability of ignition time was observed, knowing that the length of the regressing surface strongly depends on this parameter. The ignition process will be improved for more consistent ignition of the autophage engine, and the regression length was modeled to design the autophage combustion chamber. In parallel, the insertion system was developed and tested. Unacceptable power loss due to friction led to change the design to remove the largest contributor to the loss and will be tested again before integration to the autophage engine. Once integrated, the autophage engine will be able to validate all the critical functions (ignition and stable thrust, propellant insertion and dynamic sealing, throttleability) of autophage propulsion in the propulsion aspect, while the flight of AMBRE will demonstrate a concrete use of the solid propellant as the rocket's fuselage. This project encompasses work on all functional aspects of the hybrid autophage concept and aims to validate TRL4. Once done, the project will be joined by laboratory results and simulations on the cryogenic use case, verifying the viability of well known thermoplastics as a fuselage for an orbital launcher. To be continued.

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